

Bridging FAIR and Function: The Science Gateway Advantage

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Abstract—Science gateways play a critical role in modern research by integrating computational tools, data resources, and collaborative capabilities into accessible web-based platforms. While many gateways support aspects of the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) by design, achieving full FAIR compliance across their layered architectures remains a complex and evolving challenge. This paper explores the dual role science gateways play in being FAIR and enabling FAIRness in the digital objects they host or generate. We present recommendations for implementing FAIR principles within science gateway frameworks, emphasizing persistent identifiers, metadata standards, open protocols, licensing, and provenance tracking. We further examine the emerging practice of using badging to incentivize FAIR alignment. Badging can promote community trust and drive continuous improvement when backed by robust criteria and transparent verification. Through examples from projects like FAIRsharing, QUBES, Galaxy, and DesignSafe, we illustrate current FAIR practices and identify areas for future development. Our findings are informed by the Research Data Alliance’s FAIR for Virtual Research Environments (FAIR for VREs) working group and offer actionable insights for developers, maintainers, and stakeholders aiming to embed FAIR deeply and sustainably into science gateways.

Index Terms—science gateways, FAIR principles, badging, virtual research environments

I. INTRODUCTION

Science gateways—also referred to as virtual research environments or research platforms—have become essential interfaces between scientific communities and advanced cyberinfrastructure. These platforms often lower the technical barrier for engaging with data, tools, and computing environments, inherently supporting aspects of the FAIR principles: they facilitate discovery, provide consistent access, and often integrate standardized services [1]. However, while gateways may appear FAIR-compliant on the surface, aligning fully with FAIR principles is a complex task on several levels. As demonstrated in previous work [2], achieving genuine FAIRness is not automatic and requires more than technical capabilities. It involves thoughtful data architecture, rich metadata support, long-term planning for sustainability, and active coordination with domain communities to ensure shared semantics and reusability across contexts [3]. Without a deliberate strategy,

a gateway can provide access without actual interoperability or reusability, limiting its broader scientific impact. One promising strategy to operationalize FAIR principles in science gateway environments is the adoption of FAIR assessment and recognition mechanisms, such as badging systems. These frameworks offer a structured way to evaluate how well a platform supports findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse—not just for data but for software, workflows, and services. For instance, the nanoHUB platform [4], built on the Hubzero framework [5], has implemented persistent identifiers and rich metadata for simulation tools, enabling formal citation and greater visibility within research outputs. Still, making metadata meaningful across disciplines, managing long-term hosting of digital artifacts, and aligning with evolving standards remain complex challenges. Badging systems highlight where improvements are needed, such as incomplete provenance, absent licensing information, or insufficient API documentation, and encourage continuous advancement rather than one-time compliance. This incremental model fosters a culture of sustained FAIRness, where science gateways evolve alongside the research practices they support. The real value lies in labeling a science gateway as FAIR-aligned when the team hosting the science gateway and community using the science gateway has incorporated FAIR thinking into its infrastructure and community workflows. FAIR badges are beginning to shift the conversation from passive adherence to active engagement with FAIR best practices, supporting gateways in meeting standards and evolving with them.

The following discussion was started in the Research Data Alliance 22nd Plenary in the Virtual Research Environment Interest Group session: “VREs/Virtual Labs/Science Gateways: How could FAIRness badges for providers, developers, and users of VREs look like?” It set the stage for this paper and our conclusions.

II. BACKGROUND

Science gateways are web-based platforms that provide streamlined access to advanced computational tools, data resources, and collaborative environments. They integrate various cyberinfrastructure (CI) components—such as high-performance computing, data visualization, and workflow sys-

tems—into user-friendly interfaces tailored to specific research or educational communities [3].

A. FAIR Standards

In 2016, the ‘FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship’ were published in *Scientific Data* [6]. The authors intended to provide guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. Referred to as the FAIR principles, the publication has created an energetic uptake in the research community from research domains to computational sciences and led to many projects and initiatives, such as the GO FAIR initiatives worldwide in different countries.

Furthermore, people started to work on defining FAIR guidelines in more detail for different digital assets: data, software, workflows, and hardware, to name a few. While there is a large agreement in the community that FAIR is essential, how to start to make the different digital assets FAIR needs a lot of more discussions and work (see examples of around 10 interest and working groups at the Research Data Alliance (RDA) concerned with FAIR) [7]. The working group FAIR for Virtual Research Environments (FAIR for VREs) discusses the aspects of VREs, also referred to as science gateways, and addresses that the different levels of science gateways make FAIR measures complex: there is the science gateway framework itself that can be FAIR, then data and tools, thus software, embedded in science gateways, can be FAIR. Science gateway instances for a community can be FAIR, including components such as workflow engines and external data sources. FAIR is an approach that cannot be solved with a one-fits-all approach, and researchers and educators might not want all aspects of their data FAIR before publication, for example.

Good starts are guidelines developed by GO FAIR initiatives, FAIR working groups, and FAIR evaluation services such as FAIRsharing.org and FAIRshake.cloud. See here for updates on the next steps of the FAIR for VREs working group. This podcast discusses the beginning of the working group, challenges and refers to partners like SGX3 - The Center of Excellence for Science Gateways [8] - to inform the community.

B. The Role of FAIR Principles with Science Gateways

FAIR principles play a critical role in maximizing the value and usability of science gateways. On one level, the gateways as software frameworks and service platforms should be discoverable, accessible via standardized protocols, and architected for reuse and integration with other systems. On another level, they must also support the FAIRness of the digital assets they host and generate, including datasets, workflows, and software tools.

However, implementing FAIR in science gateways is not trivial. A gateway’s layered architecture—spanning frameworks, services, community instances, and embedded tools—means that FAIR compliance must be considered across multiple dimensions. For instance, the gateway’s metadata

must include persistent identifiers; hosted datasets should be described using community standards; APIs should support interoperability; and licensing, provenance, and citation mechanisms must be clearly defined and machine-readable.

The teams designing and hosting science gateways must integrate FAIR with community requests and privacy concerns. Some communities might have a policy that they don’t expose pre-publication data or are working with data that is conditioned with reuse governance requirements that are novel. As such, FAIR cannot be a one-size-fits-all solution. To these cases, the principles can be reviewed by the teams and community experts and incorporated to the best of the ability that fits the purpose of the science gateway, audience, and domain.

Initiatives such as GO FAIR [9], FAIRsharing.org [10], and FAIRshake.cloud [11] provide valuable starting points, and the FAIR for Virtual Research Environments (FAIR for VREs) working group continues to refine guidance specific to science gateways. Continued dialogue between developers, users, and policymakers is essential to embed FAIR meaningfully into gateway design and practice.

III. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FAIR SCIENCE GATEWAYS

To effectively implement FAIR principles in science gateways (VREs), we need to address both the platforms themselves and the digital objects they host and manage. This dual focus means that science gateways must not only be FAIR in their own right—through discoverable services, transparent access protocols, and reusable architectures—but also act as enablers of FAIRness for data, software, workflows, and other research outputs they generate or curate. A first step toward findability is assigning globally unique and persistent identifiers (PIDs) to the gateway platform and its components and outputs. Registries and discovery portals—whether general-purpose or discipline-specific—can be leveraged to increase visibility. Rich, community-endorsed metadata should accompany both the gateway itself and all hosted digital resources. This ensures that users, whether human or machine, can locate and understand both the infrastructure and the products of its use. Accessibility requires open and standardized communication protocols and clarity around access conditions. Even when authentication is necessary, users should be able to understand how to access a gateway or its outputs. Landing pages and metadata should remain accessible even if services are deprecated. Interoperability is central to the integration of science gateways within broader research ecosystems. Gateways should adopt community standards for metadata, data formats, and APIs, and where possible, align with established ontologies and vocabularies. Outputs should be annotated with persistent identifiers not just for the objects themselves but also for related entities such as researchers (e.g., ORCID), institutions, grants, and other research artifacts. This creates a web of linked information that enables richer interpretation and reuse. For reusability, gateways must support appropriate licensing, documentation, and provenance. Whether a gateway is provided as a service or a software package, clear and

machine-readable license terms should be provided. The use of standards like SPDX or PROV-O for tracking software components and data lineage help support reproducibility and trust. Additionally, providing citation guidance and versioning practices ensures that gateway resources can be properly attributed and reused in new contexts. These recommendations underscore that achieving FAIRness in science gateways is not a one-time task but an ongoing process. Designing and hosting a FAIR aligned science gateway requires time, discussion, and planning from the developers, community, and thought leaders on policy. However, with further adoption and examples for the community to review of science gateways using badges or practicing FAIR principles, enables growth in the adoption within future ecosystems.

IV. BADGING SYSTEMS IN SCIENCE GATEWAYS

An intriguing aspect of science gateways is the use of badging systems to recognize and certify achievements within the research community. Badges can serve multiple purposes, including signaling participation, establishing credibility, and certifying skills or accomplishments. These badges motivate researchers and provide a transparent way to display underlying data and verification processes.

A. Creating Badges for FAIR

Creating badges that reflect the FAIR principles involves several steps:

- Define Badge Categories:
 - Signaling Badges: Indicate a researcher’s engagement with FAIR practices. These badges can highlight contributions such as depositing data in a FAIR-compliant repository or participating in training on FAIR principles.
 - Participation Badges: Acknowledge contributions to FAIR-compliant projects or initiatives. For instance, involvement in collaborative projects that emphasize data sharing and interoperability can be recognized with these badges.
 - Credibility Badges: Certify that specific datasets or tools meet FAIR criteria. These badges verify that data is well-documented, easily accessible, and can be integrated with other datasets.
 - Certification Badges: Verify that a researcher or a project adheres to established FAIR standards. These might involve third-party audits or evaluations by recognized authorities in the field.
- Set Clear Criteria: Establish explicit criteria for earning each type of badge. For example, a credibility badge for FAIR might require a dataset to be indexed in a recognized repository, include comprehensive metadata, and be accessible through standardized protocols. Clear criteria ensure that badges are awarded based on measurable and verifiable achievements.
- Verification Processes: Ensure that badges are linked to verifiable information. This means implementing processes to check that the criteria have been met before

Fig. 1. Figure 1: Process of creating badges that reflect the steps a community takes to integrate badges for FAIR principles into a science gateway.

a badge is awarded. These processes might include peer review, automated validation checks, or audits by FAIR experts. Verification adds a layer of accountability and trust to the badging system.

- Link Badges to Metadata: Each badge should connect to detailed metadata about the criteria it certifies. For example, a badge could link to a repository record documenting how the dataset meets FAIR principles. This transparency helps build trust in the badge system, as users can see the specific actions and standards that the badge represents.
- Design and Branding: Develop a clear and consistent design for the badges. The design should be easily recognizable and convey the significance of the badge. Including logos of certifying bodies or institutions can enhance credibility. A well-designed badge system is functional and visually appealing, encouraging widespread adoption and use.
- Integration with science gateways: Implement the badge system within the science gateways so that badges can be easily awarded, displayed, and shared. This might involve integrating badging platforms with the science gateway’s existing infrastructure and workflows. Seamless integration ensures that the badge system becomes a natural part of the research process rather than an additional burden.

V. ENSURING TRUST AND TRANSPARENCY THROUGH FAIR

For badges to be effective, they must be trusted by the research community. This means ensuring that badges are not merely decoration objects but are backed by verification processes. Badges are designed to be tools to communicate to science gateway users about the attributes of metadata available in a provided resource on the science gateway. To ensure trust and transparency in a badging system, science gateways can implement technical approaches in their frameworks to meet community standards and openly communicate with their audiences how FAIR standards can be applied through the guided recommendations below through the representation of database and metadata cataloging and search engine optimization as a focus. 1) Provenance Tracking: Develop a data and

metadata cataloging framework with history tracking in the database. Enable users of the science gateway to see product metadata, including original authors and contributors, modification history and rationale for changes, version controls, licenses, associated DOIs, tagging, and lineage of materials around the product to be included in all metadata.

- DOI assignment: F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier; A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
- Metadata assignments: F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- Metadata descriptors: F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the data they describe
- Detailed provenance: R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

2) Indexed metadata for the science gateway's search engine: Enable the metadata of the science gateway's products to be indexed and support field searchability by these metadata types for accessibility and discovery of similar products.

- Metadata indexing: F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource; A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- Common Metadata Language: I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.; I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
- Shared Metadata Vocabularies: I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles; R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
- Metadata meets community standards: R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

3) Transparency in access: Design the science gateway framework to support open sharing of access for data and metadata, continuity of data and metadata, and community validation of access with clear access documentation.

- Access control: A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
- Data and metadata continuity: A2. Metadata is accessible, even when the data are no longer available
- Licensing of access: R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

4) Ethics-enhanced FAIR: Extend FAIR principles to consider ethical applications, including guidance and knowledge sharing to the community on what open access and open data mean and appropriate use; include design principles for use by all stakeholders and clear boundaries between open sharing and protected information sharing. Open communication enables trust to form with community standards and FAIR principles.

By implementing these recommendations, science gateways and frameworks building science gateways can ensure these research products are handled with trust and transparency with widespread adoption.

VI. FAIR EXAMPLES

The scientific community has extensive resources around applying FAIR and these standards to data products. However, we have limited visibility into science gateways past the user interfaces and published knowledge of their use of FAIR along with their educational materials. Several examples of projects and science gateways with public evidence of their approaches toward openness and FAIR standard implementation include FAIRsharing.org, QUBES, Galaxy Project, and DesignSafe. These are just a few science gateways that are identified by the Science Gateways Community Institute [12]–[15] and Science Gateways Center of Excellence [16], two United States National Science Foundation [17] awards focused on science gateways. Additional science gateways have been documented in the community by these projects to be included in a featured listing of a catalog and storybook of projects [18].

A. FAIRsharing.org

FAIRsharing.org is a standards, database, policies, and education repository for the open science and data community. An active resource for multi-disciplines, FAIRsharing guides consumers, producers, and users to access data management tasks, adopt widely used solutions and resources, and provide metadata standards that are interrelated to databases and policies. For developers and curators, there are resources and best practices for incorporating metadata standards, FAIR indicators, and other metadata schemas [19]. As described by Sandström, Lister, and Sansone, FAIR indicators indicate a product being ready for suitable use, in development, deprecated, or uncertain of value [20].

B. QUBES platform

The Quantitative Undergraduate Biology Education and Synthesis (QUBES) platform is a project of BioQUEST [21]. QUBES is a social cyberinfrastructure for the biology and educational community to contribute an open and inclusive space for STEM education reform. The platform enables educators and students to access resources, community spaces, and community-building services offered by the BioQUEST team. Within the community-contributed resources, community members can see FAIR's attributes in play with a DOI assigned to each resource, clear authorship, licensing, versioning, keywords, alignment tagging, and more. Other community interactive elements are also available through the QUBES platform, such as open information on how other community members, a section for community comments, links to the products, ability to download the resource, and metrics around the resource have adapted the resource. While there are no direct badges in the QUBES platform, there are clear metadata and data elements that do illustrate good practices of FAIR sharing and the ability to incorporate badges if desired by this community.

C. Galaxy Project

The Galaxy Project is a free, open-source science gateway platform that a diverse domain audience uses with a deep usage

in the biology community for analyzing data and authoring workflows [22]. The Galaxy Project offers its open-source community a training academy. In the training academy, the project provides a variety set of FAIR hands-on materials for learning about FAIR and applying the standards [23]. The FAIR Data, Workflows, and Research offers a complete lesson guide for the Galaxy Project community. Topics cover data management solutions, metadata, workflows in GitHub best practices, data registration, access, and persistent identifiers. These hands-on guides enable their community members to prepare the most important products, data, and products to be consumable and meet the FAIR standards through the Galaxy Project. While there are no direct badges in examples of Galaxy Projects, there could be extensions within the community that the open source community could be exploring.

D. DesignSafe

The DesignSafe science gateway is a cyberinfrastructure enabling a specific audience, in this case researchers studying natural and Earth-impacted disasters, to access open resources in the form of data in a data depot [24]–[27]. Researchers can analyze the data available on DesignSafe with the ability to launch simulations of models to analyze the data and visualize the results. The DesignSafe’s Data Depo Repository is also an approved Core Trust Seal repository which elevates the repository and sharing of resources within the science gateway [28]. Similar to the QUBES platform, datasets listed in the Data Depot have a DOI assigned to each dataset, clear authorship, licensing, versioning, and keywords. Similar to QUBES, DesignSafe also includes metrics, an area for comments or feedback, descriptions, links to the products, ability to download the dataset, and date of publication. While there are no direct badges in the DesignSafe Data Depot, there are clear metadata and data elements that do illustrate good practices of FAIR sharing and the ability to incorporate badges if desired by this community.

VII. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Despite the outlined benefits, establishing and maintaining a badging system within a science gateway is far from straightforward. Because science gateways vary significantly from technology stack to technology stack, badging adoption and evaluation can be difficult. Adopting badges into existing cyberinfrastructure workflows requires time from research software engineers and expertise from usability specialists to confirm that users understand the meaning of the badges based on audience knowledge. For badges to carry weight, they must be recognized and respected by both users and funders, which requires efforts to build trust in the criteria and system consistency. Maintaining the relevance of badges over time also demands periodic review and updates by the community. Especially as standards evolve and new good practices emerge. Addressing these complexities requires collaboration between gateway developers, domain experts, research software engineers, and policy stakeholders. It also calls for innovation in assessing FAIR alignment—not as a static checklist but as

an evolving, context-aware process grounded in community norms.

Even with these challenges, the role of badging systems in advancing FAIR practices through science gateways is promising. As awareness grows across institutions, funding agencies, and research communities about the importance of transparency, reusability, and responsible data stewardship, the demand for tangible indicators of FAIRness is likely to increase. Badges offer a visible, intuitive mechanism for signaling a gateway’s commitment to these principles, potentially influencing funding, collaboration, and reuse decisions. With broader adoption, we can anticipate both refinement of badge criteria and more sophisticated mechanisms for assessment, such as automated validation pipelines, integration with repository metadata, and tiered or contextualized badge levels. Furthermore, as gateways become more embedded in cross-institutional research infrastructures, badging systems could play a role in aligning FAIR compliance across distributed cyberinfrastructure and ecosystems. Thus, FAIR compliance is viewed as a shared responsibility rather than a top-down mandate, enabling more meaningful improvements in how science gateways support openness, reuse, and long-term impact.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In science gateways, badge systems can promote and verify adherence to FAIR practices, fostering trust within the community regarding the products available in these ecosystems. By implementing badges, science gateways can acknowledge compliance with the FAIR principles for datasets, tools, and workflows and assess how well the science gateway meets the expectations of the broader community.

Badges used in FAIR practices foster a culture of trust and accountability, rigorous verification processes, machine-readable metadata, and open protocols that ensure transparency. When the community outlines expectations for badges to communicate to stakeholders and where improvements can be made in existing implementations, the teams hosting and developing science gateway cyberinfrastructures can establish pathways for continuous improvement. These choices by the teams then empower users to make informed decisions when choosing platforms or resources, ultimately supporting more efficient, interoperable, and reproducible science.

However, a badge system’s design and governance must be carefully considered. The process of issuing badges, including the criteria for determining who can issue them, must be developed collaboratively and openly governed to ensure fairness and avoid conflict of interest. Initiatives like SGX3 can shape these discussions by bringing together gateway developers, researchers, funders, and standards organizations to align on best practices and certification mechanisms.

As science gateways evolve and adapt to the increasingly interdisciplinary and data-driven nature of modern research, integrating FAIR-aligned badging systems will be essential. These systems have the potential to bridge technical infrastructure with community norms, reinforcing FAIR as a living,

actionable framework rather than a static set of principles. Science gateways can empower researchers to advance discovery through platforms that are functional and scalable but also transparent, trustworthy, and FAIR by design.

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